

MONITORING, SUPERVISION AND COOPERATION PROGRAM IN PREPARATION FOR ADAPTIVE EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

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ANNOTATION

Cooperative teaching pedagogy is based on improving the pedagogical process and focusing it on the personality of the student. This technology serves to create a creative environment aimed at the formation of a creative personality, to increase the quality and efficiency of education. Cooperative teaching includes the main processes of training: cooperative exchange of ideas, conversation, analysis, discussion, negotiation, performance of practical tasks, problem solving. The article describes the history of the development of cooperative pedagogy, its role in the teaching process, and opinions based on the experience.

Key words: cooperative learning, cooperative pedagogy, student, teacher, critical thinking, interactive methods, independent thinking, friendly attitude.

Collaborative teaching has been implemented in the field of pedagogy for many years. The main idea of cooperative learning is not to do something together, but to learn together. Collaborative education consists in the joint development of pedagogues and students in the process of educational activity, the ability to deeply understand each other, to feel closeness to each other, to analyze the stages of activity and the results achieved in these stages in cooperation, advanced, It is of special importance as it reflects the development ideas. In the 70s of the last century, J. Dewey put forward the idea of predicting the results and organizing practical activities in cooperative education. In the educational process, teaching in small groups was used in Germany, the Netherlands, Great Britain, Australia, Israel, and Japan. Collaborative pedagogy was developed by innovative pedagogues (Sh.A. Amonashvili, SNLisenko, IPVolkov, VFShatalov, YNIliln , etc.) emphasizing that it establishes mutual relations between the participants of the pedagogical process (teacher and students) based on the principle of humanity. 'tadi [1]. Conceptually important rules for cooperative pedagogy are expressed in the pedagogical views of A. Avloni, G'. Ghulom, KDUshinsky, ASMakarenko, VASukhomlinsky, JJRusso, Ya. Korchak, K. Rodgers and others. Today, the ideas of pedagogical cooperation are embedded in the content of pedagogical technologies and form the basis of the

"concept of 21st century education". A personal approach to the child on the basis of humanism, in the school education system, the child's personality, his undeveloped abilities, "I" have a priority. The purpose of the school is to develop existing abilities, involve a person in social activities, and develop them freely.

person-oriented (developing) technologies, the following points are important:

1. A new view of the person as the goal of education [2]: the child is a person with full rights in the school, a subject in the pedagogical process; personality development - the goal of the educational system; reflects ideas such as the basis of the goal of education to educate every free, self-expressing, well-rounded person.
2. Humanization and democratization of pedagogical relations, love for children, interest in their fate; convince the child of his own strength and talent; achieving cooperation with him in the process of pedagogical relations, legal equality of teacher and student; the child's right to free choice; the right to be wrong; represents situations such as having one's own personal point of view.
3. New interpretation of individual approach. Its content is to direct the subject not to the student, but to the child to the subject. Individual approach includes the following: avoidance of targeting students who master the material on average, being able to see the positive qualities of the person , psychological and pedagogical diagnosis of the person.
4. Forming a positive "I-concept" of the person . Self -concept is a system that forms personal behavior based on a person's ideas about himself . helps to manifest [3]. A negative self-concept (I don't like myself, I can't do anything, I don't need anyone) prevents him from achieving success in various fields of activity, worsens his academic results, and leads to the formation of negative qualities in a person. The task of the teacher is to see the perfect person in the person of each student, understand him, accept him and believe him.
5. "Why ?" and "What education?" a new approach to solving the problem. Its essence is to understand the content of education as a means of personal development. The concept of education in a modern school. Cooperative pedagogy reflects the following important ideas: turning the school of knowledge into a school of education, putting the student's personality at the center of the holistic education system, the humanistic character of education, the formation of universal and national values, the development of the child's creative ability and individuality, individual and collective carrying out education in harmony. Cooperative education is based on the following target directions [4]:
 - organization of relations based on educational cooperation, denying the pedagogical requirement;
 - individual approach to students based on humanitarian ideas;
 - achieving professional and spiritual unity during the educational process.The main idea of cooperative education is to perform tasks

together and learn together. In the application of such educational technology, attention should also be paid to the creation of educational activity in each member of the group, along with the fact that students correctly complete educational tasks in cooperation with their partners. 6. Collaborative teaching is an interactive process in which the teacher organizes effective cooperation with a group of students, individually, and a team in the educational process, and implements mutually supportive cooperation of students. Students work collaboratively in small groups on assignments and help themselves and their group mates together. Collaborative teaching methods have the following five features: 1. Students work together on a common task or studied activity, as a result of group work, the subject (material) is mastered well. 2. Students work together in small groups of 2-3 people. 3. Pupils adhere to socially accepted behavior criteria developed by the group in order to achieve the solution of common tasks or to carry out learning activities. 4. Students become independent. They manage to find solutions to common tasks. The teacher organizes and prepares work on learning activities, ensures their high-quality implementation at the required level, organizes effective use of communication methods and modern information technologies. Lessons and assignments are designed to require students to help each other. 5. Students' responsibility in the learning process increases. Where does cooperative learning begin? act together with each partner in a group ;

- given to assignments serious looking, active work
- partners with gentle and sincere in communication to be
- accepting the achievements of the whole group, including partners, as one's own and celebrating together. What does cooperative learning do for the student?
- o' of the student o' study process enriches ;
- to the students cognitive (environment universe about knowledge scope to expand, to know needs development education) information will give ;
- makes students eager to learn the material;

It is known that cooperative learning technologies have great potential in improving students' creative (research-oriented, intensive development of creative thinking) abilities. The following qualities have a great impact on the development of creativity in students:

- creative thinking;
- recognizing the value of the student;
- development of children's sensitivity to environmental influences;
- orientation to free possession of ideas and objects;
- formation of the ability to provide informed information about creative

processes;

- to develop the ability to properly justify criticism;
- promote self-esteem;
- teaching to control the feeling of fear in taking grades . Based on the

cooperative learning process, we can draw the following conclusions:

- students approach the content of the lesson creatively;
- analyzes and criticizes the information in the course of the lesson and justifies his conclusions;
- creatively applies knowledge in new situations;

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